
Status of Elementary Education in Odisha: An Analysis into Enrolment Rate

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ABSTRACT

Almost all policies and programmes on education in India have consistently recommended elementary education as the foundation stone on which the whole edifice of education stands. It is the main gateway to higher education. The present paper tries to identify Firstly, to show the status of elementary level education in Odisha. Secondly to analyse the enrolment of girls, SC and ST and dropout rate in elementary level education in Odisha. This study had used the data source from economic survey of Odisha, Economic Survey of India, Census of India 2011, Odisha primary education programme authority (OPEPA), Odisha school education programme authority (OSEPA). Study reveals that in the year 2010-11, there was 52972 primary schools in Odisha which have increased to 34923 number by the year 2018-19 with an impressive progress at elementary level.

Introduction-

Universalization of Elementary Education has been explicitly reflected in the Article 45 of the Indian Constitution as: "the state shall endeavour to provide within a period of ten years from the commencement of this Constitution for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of 14 years." The National Policy on Education (1986) and Programme of Action (1992) recommended a number of measures for qualitative improvement of standardizing levels of learning at elementary stage and so on. The Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan launched in 2001 throughout the

country is an effort to universalize access to and retention in school emphasizing the quality of elementary education. Consistent efforts have been made in the post-independence period to improve the quality of elementary education. The dimensions of quality elementary education are basic infrastructure and other facilities, suitable learning environment, teaching and teacher preparation, curriculum and teaching learning material, teaching learning process, instructional time, evaluation, monitoring and supervision and community participation and support. The major efforts in the direction of Universalization of Elementary Education at the national level by the Central Government are Operation Blackboard (OB) Scheme, District Primary Education Programme (DPEP), Mid-Day Meals (MDM) Programme, Jana Sala and Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) etc. It significant that “education is for all and not for a selected few. this concept accept that education is the birth right of every child. This means all children belonging to the rich and the poor, living in town as well as in rural areas and in places which are accessible with difficulty have to be provided facilities for elementary education. There, it is recognised as a fundamental right of all citizens in India. (Thamarasseri, 2008) India has been taking a lot of initiatives to universalize elementary education. In 1976 the 42nd constitutional amendment has brought education in the concurrent list, i.e. education is shared by the state and the centre. Article 45 of the Constitution declared that “the state shall endeavour to provide, within a period of ten years from the commencement of this constitution, for free and compulsory education for all children until the age of fourteen” (Kumar and Rustagi 2010:1 cited by Mohanty, 2017).

1.1 Elementary education in Odisha: Primary and Upper Primary education has been expanding in Odessa, especially in rural and backward areas. The state aims at providing primary schools within 1 km and Upper Primary schools within 3 km of habitations having population of more than 300 and 500 respectively. During 2012-13, there were 55,329 functional primary schools/sections (Government and Local Bodies 51,655, Government Aided 468 and un-aided private/other schools 3206) in the state with 1.35 lakh teachers and 43.41 lakh students. The average teacher pupil ratio is 1:28 (2012-13). The state government has engaged 46,327 Sikhya Sahayaka and 22,717 Gana Sikh yaks. With a view to building and improving their teaching capabilities and assuring responsible career growth, the government has introduced a career advancement policy. The dropout rate has been declined to 0.37 per cent in 2012-13 (Economic Survey, 2013-14). There are 24,234 Upper Primary schools /sections with 53.8 thousand teachers and 20.81 lakh enrolment (2012-13). During 2012-13, Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) and NET Enrolment Ration (NER) at Upper Primary levels stood at 101.83 and 91.57 per cent respectively. The dropout rate has declined to 2.36 per cent in 2012-13. The state of Odisha has promulgated the Odisha

Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Rules, 2010, on 1st April, 2010 on the basis of the model rules made by the Government of India.

Government has provided Block Grant to the 916 eligible Upper Primary Schools. Block grant of the teaching staff of 74 Madras's at the Primary level has been provided. 65.20 lakh children of 6 to 14 years age group are in schools, out of which 12.43 lakhs are SC and 18.38 lakh are ST. In 6 to 14 age group, 6.31 lakh children are out of schools and from these 0.05 lakh are from SC and 0.20 lakh are from ST communities. Grant in aid related to 1866 teaching and non-teaching staff of 692 privately managed, aided Upper Primary schools. Free text books have been supplied to all students in the elementary level in the year 2012-13. Recruitment of 14,768 Sikhya Sahayaks have been made. Two steps of uniforms have been provided to 49.60 lakh students. Computer aided education programme is implemented in 1603 UP schools. 101 ECEE centres under SSA and 322 under NPEGEL are functioning in the state. 1-20 lakh children with Special Needs (CWSN) were enrolled out of student's field 1.23 lakh children. 1.14 lakh aids and appliances have been distributed to CWSN and 51,266 numbers of ramps constructed in CWSN schools 15,610 primaries and Upper Primary School buildings and 56,824 additional classrooms have been completed under SSA and 1080 school building and 16,478 ACRS are process. 51.95 lakh students of 69,019 Primary and Upper Primary schools are covered under MDM programmers.

1.3 Background of the study

This study is taking Odisha as the case study to know the status of elementary education. As it is evident that education is considered as the prime ingredient of social development. According to 2011 census the population of Odisha comprises of 41947358 in compare to the population of India that is 1210193422. Literacy rate is one of the indicators to determine the progress of the country. According to 2011 census, the highest literate state is Kerala (with 93.91 Per cent literacy) and the lowest literacy rate is noticed in Bihar (63.82 per cent). Although Odisha has not come under the lowest literate state, the literacy rate in Odisha is 73.45 per cent which is marginally behind the literacy rate of India that is 74.04% and the male literacy rate is 82.40 per cent and the female literacy is 64.36 per cent. The male literacy rate of Odisha is more than the national literacy average of male (80%) (GOI 2011).

Literature Review-

Behera (2004): The another conducted some research study on elementary education. Let us have bird's eye view over studies and their findings. The study on functioning of Sarba Siksha Abhiyan in Odisha revealed that the progress on civil works had been very slow due to release of funds, inadequate monitoring and lack of district level conveyance of SSA with other allied development schemes. **Debraj et al (2005):** The study in Karnataka on improvement of quality of elementary education revealed that

Head Masters engaged parents and the community in discussions about school development and children's learning levels. **Reddy & Sinha (2008)**: Through the dropout rates have been reducing in recent some year but still, it is going to be raising not properly stop. He argued that the main reason behind his problem is lack of rules & regulation in way of children's right on education and problem of acceptance to the needs of frontal learner who has the optimum role for children drop –out from school. **Govinda and Bandyopadhyay (2008)**: Conducted research on "Access to Elementary Education in India Country Analytical Review" This analysis review aims at exploring trends in education access and delineating different groups, which are vulnerable to exclusion from educational opportunities at the elementary stage. This review has drawn references from series of analytical papers developed on different themes i.e, regional disparity in education, social equality and gender equality in education, problem of drop out, educational opportunities, health and nutrition, governance of education and so on. **Khan & Pandey (2012)**: Demographic features are also one of the reasons behind primary school drop-out of children. The different concluding remarks of the study expand that drop out among girls' children is more than boys, nuclear family children are dropping more from schools as compared to joint family parental illiteracy about importance of school education in student life. **Bajpai & Goyal (2014)**: Their paper entitled as "Primary Education in India: Quality and Coverage Issues". The main objective of their study to analyse the silent features of primary education in India as well as educational outcomes, both use various data sources and secondary research. The study found that the government has taken large step towards the spread of primary education. However, it has become ache to say that a lot remain to be done. The poor girls, rural in habitants and members of Scheduled Tribal and Scheduled Castes still face formidable barriers in acquiring basic education. **Kamal (2015)**: Conducted research on "Status of elementary education in India". The present paper discusses on the progress of elementary education system in India. This date is collected from the secondary data collection methods. **Satapathy (2015)**: The present study was conducted to know the quality of elementary education in Nayagarh district of Odisha. The sample of the study consisted of 24 teachers and 60 students of 12 elementary schools of Nayagarh district of Odisha data were collected through questionnaires. The data results indicate that incentives such as Mid –day meals and school uniforms were available in all schools. Supervision of the schools was done by BEOs playground and provision of electricity was available in very a smaller number of schools. **Shishigu (2016)**: conducted research on "Teacher as a key role player to induce quality education challenges and prospects". The paper aimed at examining the main challenges faced by primary schools in Addis Abad. A structured and semi structure interview was conducted with teacher participants and also an upon and closed ended questionnaire was administrated. The study found salaries

of teachers are very low which is not sufficient to meet their daily needs. Teachers were also dissatisfied to meet their daily needs. Teachers also dissatisfied with the absence good governance and schools' administration because of weak effectiveness to address teacher's demands. So, teacher's greatest satisfaction can improve the quality of primary education. **Bhutia (2016):** Their paper titled as "Status of Elementary Education in the State of Sikkim, India". The main objective their study to analyse the number of government school for the last six-year, no. of enrolment of student s of elementary level and to find out the infrastructural at government schools. This research is based on the questionnaires and un-structures interview schedule. **Majhi (2019):** This paper examines regional disparities in public provision in the enabling the people of backward region through elementary education with special reference to WODE region by using secondary data collection government publication. The study analyses using simple graphical representation of key indicator also finding a composite index for overall comparison of the status using Sudarshan lyengar methods and beta distribution for objective categorization of districts. The finding Clearly show that there exists acute disparity in education between WODC and non WODC region besides which there are certain blacker spot. **Panda(2022);** Considering the level of unemployment & weak entrepreneurship ,lack of social accountability , right citizenship and respect for diversity , and absence of ecologically sustainable behaviour at individual and organisation level in the society , it appears that the school education has not been able to meet the demand of the time government as the primary custodian of providing educational services in the country , has done a reasonably good job of providing access to education for all. The weakness in the form of poor physical infrastructure, unavailability of trained and omitted headmaster and teachers and weak governance and management system result in poor quality of education.

2.1 Objectives:

- 1)To show the status of elementary level education in Odisha.
- 2)To find out the status of Enrolment Rate at government schools in Odisha.

2.2 Methodology:

The existing study is completely cantered on the availability of secondary data from various reviewed sources for the purpose to analyse the concern topic on "Status of Elementary Education in Odisha: An analysis into Enrolment rate & Infrastructure Facility". This study had used the data source from economic survey of Odisha, Economic Survey of India, Census of India 2011, Odisha primary education programme authority (OPEPA), Odisha school education programme authority (OSEPA).

2.3 Significance of the study:

This study shows the status of elementary education in Odisha. Studying the status of elementary education in Odisha is significant for understanding the state’s educational landscape, identifying areas for improvement, and formulating policies to enhance access, quality in education. This can help policymakers, educators, and stakeholders make informed decision to address challenges such as infrastructure gaps, teacher shortages, curriculum effectiveness, and student outcomes. It lays the groundwork for all future learning. During these formative years, children develop critical thinking, problem solving abilities, and a love for learning.

Status of Elementary level Education in Odisha

3.1 Table-1 Schools by Management

School Management	Primary Only	Upper Primary Only	Primary and Upper Primary	Secondary School having primary and upper primary section	Total no of school having primary and upper primary section	Secondary Only	Total (elementary and secondary school)	Total primary school	Total upper primary school	Total Secondary school
Department of Education	3398	2245	15451	4853	55947	163	56110	33398	17696	5016
Tribal/Social Welfare Department	444	9	821	347	1621	0	1621	44	830	347
Government school	33842	2254	16272	5200	57568	163	57731	33842	18526	5363
Pvt. Aided	312	1557	34	1360	5063	111	5174	312	5191	3271
Govt. and Aided School	34154	3811	16306	8360	62631	274	62905	34154	20117	8634
Pvt. Unaided	900	119	1794	906	3719	29	2748	900	1913	935

SOURCE: OPEPA

2.4 Limitation:

Due to time constraints, we are unable to include the primary data. By inclusion of primary data, the study would have been better. Limitations of this study include the reliance on secondary data sources, which may be subject to biases and limitations inherent in the original data collection processes. Additionally, the scope of the study may be constrained by the availability and quality of data on elementary education in Odisha.

The state of elementary education in Odisha was improving, thanks to initiatives to enhance rural access to school, teacher preparation, and infrastructure. State government funding is provided by the department of education management. The total number of schools in this department that are primary and upper primary schools is 55947.

Tribal Welfare Department Schools: Run by the Tribal Welfare Department, specifically for the tribal community. There are 1621 primary schools in this department. State government oversees and provides funding for government schools. There are 57568 elementary schools in the Odisha government education system. That represents the entire Department of Education plus the Department of Tribal and Social Welfare private funding and assistance with school administration. This department has fifty-six schools. also, the government.

Table-2 Enrolment by Age category

Enrolment by Age Category 2016-17						
Category	< 6 year	6-11 years	11-14 years	>14 years	Total Enrolment	Enrolment between 6-14 years
Primary(1-5)	13446	3908816	48942	820	3972024	3957758
Upper Primary(6-8)	0	362323	1775311	88367	2226001	2137634
Elementary(1-8)	13446	4271139	182453	89187	6198025	6095392
Secondary(9-10)	0	0	287991	967289	1255280	287991
Grand Total	13446	4271139	2112244	1056476	7453305	6383383

SOURCE: OPEPA

In Table 3, enrolments by age group across different school categories are detailed. Primary level enrolment (ages 1-5) totals 3,972,024 students, with the highest enrolments in the 6-11 age group. Upper primary schools (ages 6-8) enrol 2,226,001 students, primarily in the 6-11 age range. Secondary level enrolment (ages 9-10) comprises 1,255,280 students, with the majority in the >14 age group. Overall, the data highlights the prominence of the 6-11 age groups in enrolment across elementary and upper primary levels. Elementary schools exhibit higher enrolment compared to secondary levels.

Figure-1 Year wise number of schools

SOURCE: OSEPA

With changing time period, the implementation of elementary school in the state has clearly depicted that till 2016-17 number of elementary schools increased but after that, it has a declining path. Comparing from 2009-10 (64551 elementary school) to 2018-19(66765) shows a very negligible increase in the number of elementary schools in the last ten year. In the above figure represent the total number school in the year between 2012-17 in the year 2012-13 there are 67324 school. In the year 2013-14 there are 67767 schools. as compare year 2012-13 to 2013-14 the no. of school increases and 2014-15 no. of school is 68538 and as compare to previous year 2014-15 the no. of school also increases.2015-16 no. of school is 69226 and 2016-17 no. of school is 69287. Passing the year no. of school also increase that is good for the society that helps to provides free education to everyone and available for everyone.

Figure- 2 Year wise Enrolment Rate

The data provided in both the table and figure offers a comprehensive view of the boundary wall status across government elementary schools throughout a five-year span. Starting in 2012-13, there were 34,051 completed boundary walls, alongside 10,121 walls that remained incomplete. This pattern persisted in 2013-14, with 34,274 walls completed and 9,628 incomplete. However, a notable shift occurred in 2014-15, witnessing a decrease in completed walls to 27,134, with 8,021 incomplete. Subsequently, 2015-16 experienced a further decline in completed walls to 15,498, while incomplete walls surged to 19,991. By 2016-17, completed boundary walls dwindled to 18,807, while incomplete walls rose to 15,604. This consistent downward outcome in completed boundary walls underscores a worrisome trajectory in infrastructure development within government elementary schools, suggesting potential hurdles in construction and upkeep endeavour.

Table-3

DISTRICT WISE LITERACY RATES AS PER 2011 CENSUS

S L.	DISTRICT	TOTAL ALL COMMUNITIES			S.T.			S.C.		
		TOTAL	MAL	FEM	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
1	ANGUL	77.53	85.98	68.84	61.86	72.55	51.19	70.45	80.27	60.42
2	BALASORE	79.79	87.00	72.28	50.06	61.47	38.71	72.79	82.16	63.12
3	BARGARH	74.62	83.68	65.38	64.86	75.47	54.30	68.43	78.47	58.27
4	BHADRAK	82.78	89.64	75.83	43.49	53.21	33.60	74.03	84.07	63.89
5	BOLANGIR	64.72	75.85	53.50	54.93	67.78	42.34	63.42	74.23	52.52

6	BOUDH	71.61	83.34	59.79	63.84	77.88	50.17	66.90	79.54	54.29
7	CUTTACK	85.50	91.11	79.55	57.93	68.87	46.49	76.08	84.89	66.91
8	DEOGARH	72.57	81.92	63.05	62.38	73.17	51.67	67.63	87.00	57.16
9	DHENKANAL	78.76	86.18	71.00	60.39	70.82	50.04	71.47	80.86	61.87
10	GAJAPATI	53.49	64.38	43.18	43.66	55.39	32.83	51.03	62.40	40.45
11	GANJAM	71.09	80.99	61.13	49.71	60.71	38.89	59.62	72.31	47.22
12	JAGATSINGHPUR	86.59	92.38	80.63	66.55	76.06	55.50	78.33	86.58	69.95
13	JAJPUR	80.13	86.84	73.29	47.60	59.68	35.48	70.30	79.29	61.20
14	JHARSUGUDA	78.86	86.61	70.73	68.72	78.78	58.70	74.79	83.97	65.53
15	KALAHANDI	59.22	71.90	46.68	49.29	63.31	35.84	61.97	73.59	50.29
16	KANDHAMAL	64.13	76.93	51.94	58.34	72.12	45.58	66.12	78.88	53.90
17	KENDRAPADA	85.15	91.45	78.96	62.39	70.70	54.01	75.16	84.34	56.99
18	KEONJHAR	68.24	78.12	58.28	53.24	65.22	41.56	73.77	83.81	63.78
19	KHORDHA	86.88	91.78	81.61	69.33	79.49	58.64	78.82	84.99	68.36
20	KORAPUT	49.21	60.32	38.55	35.66	46.20	25.37	52.64	64.72	41.50
21	MALKANGIRI	48.54	59.07	38.28	35.23	44.91	26.25	65.59	75.82	55.12
22	MAYURBHANJ	63.17	73.76	52.71	53.11	65.28	41.36	66.06	65.40	55.88
23	NABARANPUR	46.43	57.31	35.80	38.54	49.46	28.02	57.61	67.73	47.60
24	NAYAGARH	80.42	88.16	72.05	66.29	78.62	54.20	71.59	81.49	61.25
25	NUAPADA	57.35	70.29	44.76	51.01	75.13	37.73	60.03	72.40	47.97
26	PURI	84.67	90.85	78.28	74.62	83.08	64.71	75.77	84.60	66.77
27	RAYAGADA	49.76	61.04	39.19	36.69	47.87	26.72	53.48	66.19	41.46
28	SAMBALPUR	76.22	84.35	67.93	65.76	76.00	55.59	72.08	81.69	62.38
29	SONEPUR	74.42	84.40	64.04	66.78	77.38	56.05	70.34	80.95	59.29
30	SUNDARGARH	73.34	81.01	65.08	65.08	73.98	56.39	70.92	79.75	62.03
	ODISHA	72.87	81.59	64.01	52.24	63.70	41.20	69.02	79.21	58.76

SOURCE: OSEPA

In accordance with the 2011 census among the 30 districts in the state, literacy rate of Khordha district (among all category) is highest at 86.88% and Nawarangpur district has the lowest at 46.43% District like Jagatsinghpur, Purl, Kendrapad, Bhadrak, Cuttack, Nayagarh are in good performance category in term of literacy whereas Rayagada, Koraput, Nuapada, Malkangiri, and Kalahandi are under

the less performing district. Under the male literacy rate Jagatsinhapur (92.38%) has highest and Nawarangpur (57.31%) has the lowest among all district where as in female literacy rate Khordha (81.61%) has the maximum and Nawarangpur (35.23%) has the minimum literacy rate in the state. Apart from this, the category wise literacy rate among SC and ST show that the Purl district (74.62%) of the state has the highest literacy among the ST category and Malkangiri district (35.23%) has the lowest literacy. Similarly, among the SC category Jagatsingpur district (78.33%) has the highest literacy rate and Ganjam district (51.03%) has the lowest in term of category division rate and Ganjam district.

Figure-3 3

Findings:

Another important outcome achieved from the data is that there is a notable extent in term of the primary school's appearance in Odisha. In the year 2010-11, there was 52972 primary schools in Odisha which have increased to 34923 number by the year 2018-19 with an impressive progress at elementary level. The education system in Odisha has experienced a rapid growth in the last two decades, but even after seven decades in independent still district like Kandhmal, Nabarangpur, Bolangir, Koraput, Rayagada, Malakangiri, Sundargarh, Mayurbhanj, Kalahandi, Kendrapara, are lacking behind a far away from the achievement of proper education. Elementary education reveal that from 2009-10 to 2018-19 many districts are improved because of scheme like Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) 2001-02, District Primary Education Programme (DPEP 1994), Universalization of elementary education (UEE) etc. Despite the effective implementation of those schemes in Odisha still district like Rayagada, Malakangiri, Kalahandi, Kandhmala, Koraput, Bolangir, Kenrapara, Keonjhar, Cuttack are under the position of high drop-out at elementary level school education.

Summary & Conclusion:

The study comprise 30 districts came to the ultimate results that from the period of independence there is a rapid transformation seen in case of literacy & elementary enrolment but in the last five years the major concern like elementary enrolment of children, school drop-out, completion rate, repetition rate has changes. Therefore, through observing and analysing the above implied data source and policy suggestions by the government it is needless to say that, the status of the prevailing factual condition of the elementary education system which includes both primary and upper primary school level in Odisha is not very impactful as well a satisfactory at all. The main reason behind this reduction in elementary enrolment is the socio-economic inequalities among different regions of the state which resulting some regions growing more by the opportunity cost of other regions. Major problem like persistent poverty of parents, financial crisis, a long distance from school, lack of interest among students for study, parents' burden to work with them, taking care of a small child, teacher's behaviour, school infrastructural facilities, grade repetition at same class, poor health, etc. are the prominent issues in the way of achieving universalization of elementary education in Odisha.

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